

Investigation of Effective Cross Section Generation in FRENDY-V2/GENESIS for Three-Dimensional LWR Lattice Problems

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the generation of multi-group effective cross sections (XSs) using FRENDY-V2/GENESIS for applications to three-dimensional light-water reactor (LWR) lattice calculations. Particular attention was paid to the theoretical treatment of neutron escape probability in finite-height fuel geometries. An optimized three-term rational approximation was evaluated because it was expected to more accurately represent neutron escape probability and thereby improve effective XSs, especially over the intermediate optical length range. Benchmark calculations were conducted for a simplified three-dimensional UO₂ fuel lattice and compared against continuous-energy Monte Carlo simulations in terms of the effective multiplication factor (*k*-effective) and the axial fission reaction rate distributions. Three key findings emerged; (1) explicitly accounting for axial variations in the Dancoff factor had a negligible impact; (2) the three-term rational approximation had a larger impact in 172-group calculations than in 361-group calculations; and (3) although the three-term approximation improved accuracy, Carlvik's two-term rational approximation without axial Dancoff variation remained preferable due to its favorable balance between computational cost and accuracy. Consequently, it was concluded that FRENDY-V2/GENESIS can achieve sufficient accuracy for the *k*-effective and the axial fission reaction rate distribution in three-dimensional LWR lattice calculations using effective XSs generated in conventional two-dimensional models.

Keywords: equivalent theory, multi-term rational approximation, neutron current method, FRENDY version 2, GENESIS

1. INTRODUCTION

Recent reactor physics simulations have trended toward high-fidelity modeling that resolves complex geometries and employs detailed multi-group energy structures. Three-dimensional neutron transport codes based on the method of characteristics (MOC) have been extensively developed. Planar MOC codes such as DeCART [1] and MPACT [2] support two-dimensional heterogeneous and three-dimensional fine-mesh calculations. SHIKOKU [3] and GENESIS [4] implement MOC in three-dimensional geometries without spatial homogenization by applying axially simplified techniques, namely the ASMOC3D and LEAF methods. In the present work, we employ a code system consisting of the nuclear data processing code FRENDY version 2 (FRENDY-V2) [5] coupled with GENESIS. FRENDY-V2 directly generates multi-group macroscopic cross sections (XSs) in KRAM-formatted files from ACE-formatted files; the neutron spectrum for an infinite homogeneous medium is obtained via an ultra-fine-group slowing-down calculation. GENESIS performs MOC-based neutron transport calculations in two- and three-dimensional geometries. A previous study demonstrated that FRENDY-V2/GENESIS can accurately evaluate neutronics parameters for two-dimensional light-water reactor (LWR) systems [6]. FRENDY-V2/GENESIS offers the following distinctive advantages: (1) direct treatment of resonance interference among different resonance nuclides within a material by performing an ultra-fine-group slowing-down calculation in a medium containing multiple nuclides

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(e.g., UO_2), zircaloy, and light water); (2) direct handling of nuclear-data perturbations, including implicit effects, in random-sampling-based uncertainty quantification; and (3) moving beyond the conventional two-step core analysis scheme to provide more rigorous deterministic neutron transport simulations.

This study investigated the generation of multi-group effective XSs to extend the applicability of FRENDY-V2/GENESIS to the three-dimensional LWR lattice calculations. Because the treatment of the Dancoff factor was addressed in a previous study [7], the present work focused on the calculation of neutron escape probability from finite-height fuel regions and resulting effective XSs.

2. EFFECTIVE CROSS SECTION GENERATION IN FRENDY-V2/GENESIS

The Dancoff factor is used to account for the spatial shadowing effect among resonance absorbers. For a two-dimensional fuel lattice, it can be evaluated with the neutron current method, where the Dancoff factor is defined as the ratio of neutron fluxes obtained from one-group fixed-source calculations in 'isolated' and 'lattice' geometries, as illustrated in Figure 1 [8]. In these calculations, resonance absorbers such as the fuel pellet are treated as 'black' (i.e., perfectly absorbing) regions.

In similar manner, reference [7] constructed corresponding isolated and lattice models for a three-dimensional fuel lattice, as illustrated in Figure 2. As reported in reference [7], the Dancoff factor in the end region of the fuel rod (i.e., adjacent to top/bottom reflectors) can differ significantly from that in the axial mid-plane because the axial neutron-leakage conditions are different. In the present work, however, resonance self-shielding is treated for an isolated fuel pin; lattice effects are taken into account only through the Dancoff factor evaluated by the above procedure.

The background XSs are calculated based on Carlvik's two-term rational approximation [9]. The escape XS is derived from the geometry as the reciprocal of the average chord length defined as $4V/S$, where V is the volume and S is the surface area. Two background XSs are prepared for FRENDY-V2, and the target effective macroscopic XSs used in GENESIS are obtained as a weighted average of the effective macroscopic XSs computed with these two background XSs.

Figure 1. Isolated/Lattice models for 2D fuel lattice Figure 2. Isolated/Lattice models for 3D fuel lattice

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Conventional Method for Lattice Physics Computations

As described in reference [9], the escape probability from an isolated fuel lump is given as follows:

$$P_e(E) = \frac{1}{4\pi\Sigma_{t,f}(E)V_f} \int_{\vec{n}\cdot\vec{\Omega}>0} d\vec{\Omega} \int_S dS(\vec{n}\cdot\vec{\Omega}) \{1 - \exp(-\Sigma_{t,f}(E)l)\}, \quad (1)$$

where P_e , V_f , S , $\Sigma_{t,f}$, l , and E are the escape probability, the volume of a fuel lump, the surface area of a fuel lump, the macroscopic total XS of a fuel lump, the track length of neutron in a fuel lump (i.e., the chord length), and the neutron energy, respectively. The probability density function of the chord length $f(l)$ and the average chord length \bar{l} are given as follows:

$$f(l)dl = \int_l^{l+dl} d\vec{\Omega} \int_S dS(\vec{n}\cdot\vec{\Omega}) / \int_{\vec{n}\cdot\vec{\Omega}>0} d\vec{\Omega} \int_S dS(\vec{n}\cdot\vec{\Omega}), \quad (2)$$

$$\bar{l} = \int_0^{\infty} l f(l) dl = \frac{4V_f}{S}. \quad (3)$$

Using Equations (2) and (3), Equation (1) can be rewritten as follows:

$$P_e(E) = \frac{1}{\Sigma_{t,f}(E)\bar{l}} \int_0^{\infty} dl f(l) \{1 - \exp(-\Sigma_{t,f}(E)l)\}. \quad (4)$$

On N -term rational approximation, the distribution function of the chord length is approximately given as a summation of the exponential functions and then the escape probability is obtained as follows:

$$f(l) dl = \sum_{n=1}^N c_n \exp(-d_n l) dl, \quad (5)$$

$$P_e(E) = \frac{1}{\Sigma_{t,f}(E)\bar{l}} \int_0^{\infty} dl \sum_{n=1}^N c_n \exp(-d_n l) \{1 - \exp(-\Sigma_{t,f}(E)l)\} = \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{b_n a_n}{\Sigma_{t,f}(E)\bar{l} + a_n}, \quad (6)$$

where the coefficients of a_n , b_n , c_n , and d_n satisfy $a_n = d_n \bar{l}$ and $b_n a_n = c_n / d_n$. Because the escape probability is approaching unity in the white limit with very small optical length $\Sigma_{t,f}(E)\bar{l}$, $\sum_{n=1}^N b_n = 1$ is obtained for the coefficient of b_n . In the black limit with very large optical length $\Sigma_{t,f}(E)\bar{l}$, Wigner's single-term rational approximation (i.e., Equation (6) with $N = 1$) gives an accurate escape probability, thus the coefficients of a_n and b_n satisfy $\sum_{n=1}^N b_n a_n = 1$.

3.2. Discussion for Three-Dimensional Computations

Discussions of neutron escape probability have focused on infinite-height geometries (e.g., an infinite slab, cylinder, or hollow cylinder). For three-dimensional calculations, it is necessary to account for neutron escape probability in finite-height geometries.

Firstly, let us consider the distribution function of the chord length. As an example of infinite and finite-height geometries, cylinder geometries with a radius of 0.5 cm, and a height of 1.0 cm or an infinite-height were focused on. Figure 3 shows the chord length frequency obtained from a Monte Carlo calculation with one million samples, presented as a histogram with a bin width of 0.01 cm. Notably, although the distribution extends beyond 3.0 cm, Figure 3(a) is truncated at 3.0 cm.

Figure 3. Frequency of chord length in infinite and finite cylinder geometries.

As Figure 3 indicates, the chord length in finite cylinder geometry distributes over a finite interval. In this case, the maximum value of chord length was $\sqrt{2}$. Thus, let us assume the distribution function of the chord length is same as Equation (5) and change the integration interval in Equation (4) to be consistent with the situation in the finite-height geometry with the maximum chord length L as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_e(E) &= \frac{1}{\Sigma_{t,f}(E)\bar{l}} \int_0^L dl f(l) \{1 - \exp(-\Sigma_{t,f}(E)l)\} \\
 &= \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{b_n a_n}{\Sigma_{t,f}(E)\bar{l} + a_n} - \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{b_n a_n}{\Sigma_{t,f}(E)\bar{l}} e^{-\frac{a_n L}{\bar{l}}} + \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{a_n}{\Sigma_{t,f}(E)\bar{l}} \frac{b_n a_n}{\Sigma_{t,f}(E)\bar{l} + a_n} e^{-(\Sigma_{t,f}(E)L + \frac{a_n L}{\bar{l}})}.
 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Then, let us consider the white limit to obtain a constraint to be satisfied by the coefficients of a_n and b_n . The Taylor expansion up to the first-order term was applied to third term on the right-hand side in Equation (7) as follows:

$$\sum_{n=1}^N \frac{a_n}{\Sigma_{t,f}(E)\bar{l}} \frac{b_n a_n}{\Sigma_{t,f}(E)\bar{l} + a_n} e^{-(\Sigma_{t,f}(E)L + \frac{a_n L}{\bar{l}})} \approx \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{b_n a_n}{\Sigma_{t,f}(E)\bar{l}} e^{-\frac{a_n L}{\bar{l}}} \left(1 - \frac{\Sigma_{t,f}(E)\bar{l}}{a_n} - \Sigma_{t,f}(E)L\right). \quad (8)$$

Thus, the following condition was given:

$$\lim_{\Sigma_{t,f}(E)\bar{l} \rightarrow 0} P_e(E) \approx \sum_{n=1}^N b_n - \sum_{n=1}^N b_n e^{-\frac{a_n L}{\bar{l}}} - \sum_{n=1}^N b_n a_n \frac{L}{\bar{l}} e^{-\frac{a_n L}{\bar{l}}} = 1. \quad (9)$$

Let us also consider the black limit based on the assumption that Equation (7) becomes asymptotic to the escape probability given by Wigner's single-term rational approximation as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\lim_{\Sigma_{t,f}(E)\bar{l} \rightarrow \infty} \left\{ \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{b_n a_n}{\Sigma_{t,f}(E)\bar{l} + a_n} - \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{b_n a_n}{\Sigma_{t,f}(E)\bar{l}} e^{-\frac{a_n L}{\bar{l}}} + \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{a_n}{\Sigma_{t,f}(E)\bar{l}} \frac{b_n a_n}{\Sigma_{t,f}(E)\bar{l} + a_n} e^{-(\Sigma_{t,f}(E)L + \frac{a_n L}{\bar{l}})} \right\} \\
 &\approx \lim_{\Sigma_{t,f}(E)\bar{l} \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\Sigma_{t,f}(E)\bar{l} + 1} = 0.
 \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

The necessary and sufficient condition for matching up to the term of $\Sigma_{t,f}(E)^{-1}$ is obtained as follows:

$$\sum_{n=1}^N b_n a_n \left(1 - e^{-\frac{a_n L}{\bar{l}}}\right) = 1. \quad (11)$$

When the case of $N = 1$ was considered for simplicity, $a_1 = 0.16208$ and $b_1 = 21.206$ were obtained by Equations (9) and (11), and the escape probability was represented as follows:

$$P_e(E) = \frac{b_1 a_1}{\Sigma_{t,f}(E)\bar{l} + a_1} - \frac{b_1 a_1}{\Sigma_{t,f}(E)\bar{l}} e^{-a_1 \frac{L}{\bar{l}}} + \frac{a_1}{\Sigma_{t,f}(E)\bar{l}} \frac{b_1 a_1}{\Sigma_{t,f}(E)\bar{l} + a_1} e^{-(\Sigma_{t,f}(E)\bar{l} + a_1) \frac{L}{\bar{l}}} \quad (12)$$

Figure 4 presents the escape probability (i.e., the left-hand side of Eq. (12)), the first term on the right-hand side, and the combined contribution of the second and third terms on the right-hand side of Eq. (12). The contribution of the second and third terms becomes non-negligible when the optical length is small. However, because Eq. (7) is too cumbersome to cast into a form that can be consistently related to the background XSs in the subsequent derivations, the above approach was not pursued.

Therefore, let us next consider the improvement of conventional formula for the escape probability based on the infinite-height geometry. Figure 5 compares Eq. (12) with Wigner's single-term rational approximation. A noticeable difference in escape probability between the infinite and finite cylinder cases is observed in the intermediate optical length range. To more accurately reproduce behavior in this gray/intermediate range, reference [10] proposed a multi-term rational approximation with coefficients optimized to match the neutron flux, and reported that an optimized three-term rational approximation agrees better than Carlvik's two-term rational approximation. Accordingly, this study incorporated the approach of considering the neutron flux in the gray/intermediate optical length range to perform multi-term rational approximation.

Figure 4. Escape probability and its component breakdown in finite cylinder geometry.

Figure 5. Comparison of escape probability between finite and infinite cylinder geometries.

4. NUMERICAL CALCULATIONS

4.1. Calculation Conditions

A simplified three-dimensional problem was constructed as illustrated in Figure 6. The calculation model consisted of a UO_2 fuel and a light water moderator, and a fuel cladding was neglected for simplicity. The fuel and light water moderator compositions were taken from the UO_2 pin-cell problem in reference [11]. The fuel and moderator temperatures were set to 900 K and 600 K, respectively. The vacuum boundary condition was applied at the top surface, while the reflective boundary conditions were imposed on the side and bottom surfaces. The reference results were obtained using the continuous-energy Monte Carlo code MVP3 [12]. To reduce statistical uncertainty, twenty-five independent Monte Carlo calculations with different initial seed were performed. In each calculation, the number of histories per batch was 1×10^6 and the number of batches was 5×10^3 , excluding 100 inactive (skipped) batches (i.e. the number of total histories was 5×10^9).

Figure 6. 3D fuel-moderator geometry.

Multi-group effective macroscopic XSs for the XMAS-172 and SHEM-361 group structures [13, 14] were generated with FRENDY-V2 using JENDL-5 [15]. To determine coefficients on the three-term rational approximation, one-group fixed source calculations were performed. The macroscopic total XS in the fuel region was prescribed as a set of values equally spaced on a logarithmic scale, as follows:

$$\Sigma_{t,f} = 10^d [1/\text{cm}] \quad (d = \pm 10.0, \pm 5.0, \pm 4.0, \pm 3.0, \pm 2.0, \pm 1.9, \dots, \pm 0.1, 0.0). \quad (11)$$

The background XSs based on Wigner's single- and Carlvik's two-term rational approximation, and three-term rational approximation were estimated as follows:

$$\sigma_0^{\text{Wigner}} = \frac{D}{l \sum_{i \in \text{fuel}} N_i} \quad (12)$$

$$\sigma_0^{Carlvik} = \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^2 b_i \sqrt{\frac{a_i}{l \sum_{i \in fuel} N_i}} \right\}^2, \quad (13)$$

$$\sigma_0^{Gray} = \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^3 b'_i \sqrt{\frac{a'_i}{l \sum_{i \in fuel} N_i}} \right\}^2, \quad (14)$$

where D is the Dancoff factor evaluated by the neutron current method and N_i is the number density of nuclide i . The coefficients of a_n and b_n ($n = 1, 2$) used in Equation (13) were calculated by using the Dancoff factor. The coefficients of a'_n and b'_n ($n = 1, 2, 3$) used in Equation (14) were calculated through the optimization calculation to reproduce the neutron fluxes on the above one-group fixed source calculations. Notably, $\sum_{n=1}^3 b'_n a'_n = D$ and $\sum_{n=1}^3 b'_n = 1$ were satisfied.

The MOC-based calculation conditions in GENESIS are summarized as follows:

- ✓ Maximum ray tracing pitch is 0.025 cm,
- ✓ Number of azimuthal angle divisions in 0 to 2π is 64,
- ✓ Number of polar angle divisions in 0 to π is 8 based on Gauss-Legendre quadrature set,
- ✓ P3 anisotropic scattering is considered.

4.2. Calculation Results

Figure 7 shows the axial distributions of the Dancoff factor, background cross section, and the coefficients of the three-term rational approximation. For all parameters, the values in the axial meshes adjacent to the upper light-water region (i.e., axial meshes 16-20) differ from those in the central region (i.e., axial meshes 1-15). This indicates that the difference in neutron-leakage conditions between the two- and three-dimensional geometries arises primarily near the ends of the axial fuel region.

Figure 7. Dancoff factor, background XS, and coefficients on three-term rational approximation.

Figure 8 compares the microscopic capture XSs of ^{238}U within the 1 to 100 eV range calculated with MVP3 between 1st and 20th axial meshes. XSs in 1st axial mesh corresponded to those evaluated in a two-dimensional model (i.e., neglecting the axial variations of Dancoff factor and average chord length). Differences were mainly observed in typical resonance peak such as 133rd (83.9 to 88.8 eV), 141st (65.83 to 66.16 eV), 165th (36.42 to 36.86 eV), 184th (20.77 to 20.98 eV), and 247th (6.63 to 6.71 eV) energy groups. For the 172-group structure, the difference were approximately 6 to 10%, which was larger than those for the 361-group structure (approximately 2 to 6%).

Calculation accuracy for the effective multiplication factor (k-effective) and the axial fission reaction rate distribution was discussed. Table I summarizes the k-effective comparison, and Figure 9 presents the axial fission reaction rate distribution. Regarding the treatment of axial Dancoff-factor variation (i.e., '2D' vs '3D'), the impact on k-effective is approximately 10 pcm for the 172-group structure and 2 pcm for the 361-group structure, and is therefore practically negligible. The impact of three-term rational

approximation in 172 groups was larger than that in 361 groups. However, as discussed in reference [6], the accuracy of FRENDY-V2/GENESIS depended on the number of energy groups, and the 361-group structure is currently required. Thus, although the three-term rational approximation improved accuracy, Carlvik's two-term rational approximation without axial Dancoff factor variation (i.e., using XSs generated with a conventional two-dimensional model) remained attractive in practice because it offers a favorable trade-off between computational cost and accuracy.

Figure 8. Comparison of microscopic capture XSs of ^{238}U between 1st and 20th axial meshes.

Table I. Comparison result of k -effective (Statistical error: < 1 pcm).

Method	k -effective [-]		Relative difference [pcm]	
	172 groups	361 groups	172 groups	361 groups
MVP3 (Reference)	1.36008		---	
Wigner (2D) / (3D)	1.35765 / 1.35754	1.36099 / 1.36095	-132 / -138	50 / 48
Carlvik (2D) / (3D)	1.35299 / 1.35283	1.35962 / 1.35958	-385 / -394	-24 / -26
Gray (2D) / (3D)	1.35470 / 1.35455	1.36008 / 1.36010	-292 / -300	1 / 2

Figure 9. Comparison result of axial fission reaction rate distribution (Statistical error: $\sim 0.001\%$).

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the generation of multi-group effective XSs using FRENDY-V2/GENESIS for three-dimensional LWR lattice calculations. Based on the investigation of the theoretical formula, the optimized three-term rational approximation was initially considered as a promising approach for reproducing neutron escape probability in finite-height geometries and the resulting effective XSs especially in intermediate optical length range.

Benchmark calculations were performed for a simplified three-dimensional geometry and compared with continuous-energy Monte Carlo results for the k -effective and the axial fission reaction rate distribution, the following conclusions were obtained: (1) explicitly accounting for axial variations in the Dancoff factor had a negligible impact; (2) the three-term rational approximation, which improves

the representation in the gray/intermediate optical length range, had a more pronounced impact in 172-group calculations than in 361-group calculations; and (3) although the three-term rational approximation improved accuracy, Carlvik's two-term rational approximation without axial Dancoff dependence remained preferable in practice because of its favorable trade-off between computational cost and accuracy.

Consequently, this study found that when applying FRENDY-V2/GENESIS to three-dimensional LWR lattice problems, sufficient accuracy can be achieved by employing multi-group effective XSs generated in conventional two-dimensional models.

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